

Assessing Situated Judgment in Nursing

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What is Situated Judgment in Nursing?

“an interpretation or conclusion about a patient’s needs, concerns, or health problems, and/or the decision to take action (or not), use or modify standard approaches, or improvise new ones as deemed appropriate by the patient’s response” (Tanner, 2006, p. 204)

Situated Judgment = Clinical Judgment

It's tricky...

“Clinical judgments are more influenced by what the nurse brings to the situation than the objective data about the situation at hand” (Tanner, 2006, p. 205).

Nursing Clinical Judgment History

- Intuitive-Humanistic Model (Benner, 1984), later integrated into the Tanner Model (2006)
- Dual Process Reasoning Theory (Croskerry, 2009; Pelaccia, et al., 2011), anchored in the cognitive continuum theory (Harbison, 2001)
- Information Processing Model (Oppenheimer & Kelso, 2015).
- National Council of State Boards of Nursing (NCSBN), strictly a MCQ exam until 2023, low clinical judgment content

Tanner Model of Clinical Judgment (revised, 2022)

FIGURE 13.1 Model of Clinical Judgment (Adapted from Tanner, C. A. (2006). A research-based model of clinical judgment. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 45(6), 204–211.)

Lasater Clinical Judgment Rubric (LCJR)

- Provide a common language to talk about an abstract concept for students and faculty
- Describe a trajectory of development in prelicensure nursing students
- Serve as a formative assessment tool

Evidence-based CJ dimensions

Stages of CJ (Tanner, 2006)	Dimensions (Lasater, 2007, 2011)
Noticing	Focused observation Recognizing deviations from expected patterns Information seeking
Interpreting	Prioritizing data Making sense of data
Responding	Calm, confident manner Clear communication Well-planned intervention/flexibility Being skillful
Reflecting	Evaluation/self-analysis Commitment to improvement

The Lasater Clinical Judgment Rubric (LCJR)

LASATER CLINICAL JUDGMENT RUBRIC
Noticing and Interpreting

Effective NOTICING involves:	Exemplary	Accomplished	Developing	Beginning
Focused Observation	Focuses observation appropriately; regularly observes and monitors a wide variety of objective and subjective data to uncover any useful information	Regularly observes/monitors a variety of data, including both subjective and objective; most useful information is noticed, may miss the most subtle signs	Attempts to monitor a variety of subjective and objective data, but is overwhelmed by the array of data; focuses on the most obvious data, missing some important information	Confused by the clinical situation and the amount/type of data; observation is not organized and important data is missed, and/or assessment errors are made
Recognizing Deviations from Expected Patterns	Recognizes subtle patterns and deviations from expected patterns in data and uses these to guide the assessment	Recognizes most obvious patterns and deviations in data and uses these to continually assess	Identifies obvious patterns and deviations, missing some important information; unsure how to continue the assessment	Focuses on one thing at a time and misses most patterns/deviations from expectations; misses opportunities to refine the assessment
Information Seeking	Assertively seeks information to plan intervention: carefully collects useful subjective data from observing the client and from interacting with the client and family	Actively seeks subjective information about the client's situation from the client and family to support planning interventions; occasionally does not pursue important leads	Makes limited efforts to seek additional information from the client/family; often seems not to know what information to seek and/or pursues unrelated information	Is ineffective in seeking information; relies mostly on objective data; has difficulty interacting with the client and family and fails to collect important subjective data
Effective INTERPRETING involves:	Exemplary	Accomplished	Developing	Beginning
Prioritizing Data	Focuses on the most relevant and important data useful for explaining the client's condition	Generally focuses on the most important data and seeks further relevant information, but also may try to attend to less pertinent data	Makes an effort to prioritize data and focus on the most important, but also attends to less relevant/useful data	Has difficulty focusing and appears not to know which data are most important to the diagnosis; attempts to attend to all available data
Making Sense of Data	Even when facing complex, conflicting or confusing data, is able to (1) note and make sense of patterns in the client's data, (2) compare these with known patterns (from the nursing knowledge base, research, personal experience, and intuition), and (3) develop plans for interventions that can be justified in terms of their likelihood of success	In most situations, interprets the client's data patterns and compares with known patterns to develop an intervention plan and accompanying rationale; the exceptions are rare or complicated cases where it is appropriate to seek the guidance of a specialist or more experienced nurse	In simple or common/familiar situations, is able to compare the client's data patterns with those known and to develop/explain intervention plans; has difficulty, however, with even moderately difficult data/situations that are within the expectations for students, inappropriately requires advice or assistance	Even in simple of familiar/common situations has difficulty interpreting or making sense of data; has trouble distinguishing among competing explanations and appropriate interventions, requiring assistance both in diagnosing the problem and in developing an intervention

LASATER CLINICAL JUDGMENT RUBRIC
Responding and Reflecting

Effective RESPONDING involves:	Exemplary	Accomplished	Developing	Beginning
Calm, Confident Manner	Assumes responsibility; delegates team assignments, assess the client and reassures them and their families	Generally displays leadership and confidence, and is able to control/calm most situations; may show stress in particularly difficult or complex situations	Is tentative in the leader's role; reassures clients/families in routine and relatively simple situations, but becomes stressed and disorganized easily	Except in simple and routine situations, is stressed and disorganized, lacks control, making clients and families anxious/less able to cooperate
Clear Communication	Communicates effectively; explains interventions; calms/reassures clients and families; directs and involves team members, explaining and giving directions; checks for understanding	Generally communicates well; explains carefully to clients, gives clear directions to team; could be more effective in establishing rapport	Shows some communication ability (e.g., giving directions); communication with clients/families/team members is only partly successful; displays caring but not competence	Has difficulty communicating; explanations are confusing, directions are unclear or contradictory, and clients/families are made confused/anxious, not reassured
Well-Planned Intervention/Flexibility	Interventions are tailored for the individual client; monitors client progress closely and is able to adjust treatment as indicated by the client response	Develops interactions based on relevant patient data; monitors progress regularly but does not expect to have to change treatments	Develops interventions based on the most obvious data; monitors progress, but is unable to make adjustments based on the patient response	Focuses on developing a single intervention addressing a likely solution, but it may be vague, confusing, and/or incomplete; some monitoring may occur
Being Skillful	Shows mastery of necessary nursing skills	Displays proficiency in the use of most nursing skills; could improve speed or accuracy	Is hesitant or ineffective in utilizing nursing skills	Is unable to select and/or perform the nursing skills
Effective REFLECTING involves:	Exemplary	Accomplished	Developing	Beginning
Evaluation/Self-Analysis	Independently evaluates/analyzes personal clinical performance, noting decision points, elaborating alternatives and accurately evaluating choices against alternatives	Evaluates/analyzes personal clinical performance with minimal prompting, primarily major events/decisions; key decision points are identified and alternatives are considered	Even when prompted, briefly verbalizes the most obvious evaluations; has difficulty imagining alternative choices; is self-protective in evaluating personal choices	Even prompted evaluations are brief, cursory, and not used to improve performance; justifies personal decisions/choices without evaluating them
Commitment to Improvement	Demonstrates commitment to ongoing improvement: reflects on and critically evaluates nursing experiences; accurately identifies strengths/weaknesses and develops specific plans to eliminate weaknesses	Demonstrates a desire to improve nursing performance: reflects on and evaluates experiences; identifies strengths/weaknesses; could be more systematic in evaluating weaknesses	Demonstrates awareness of the need for ongoing improvement and makes some effort to learn from experience and improve performance but tends to state the obvious, and needs external evaluation	Appears uninterested in improving performance or unable to do so; rarely reflects; is uncritical of him/herself, or overly critical (given level of development); is unable to see flaws or need for improvement

How is the LCJR Used

- Research
- Debriefing (in simulation and clinical placements)
- Guide for questioning/feedback
- Written evaluations
- Setting goals for development

The Lasater Clinical Judgment Rubric: 17 Years Later

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BACKGROUND

ABSTRACT

Background: Nearly 17 years ago, the Lasater Clinical Judgment Rubric (LCJR) was published to provide a common language and trajectory of students' development to think like a nurse. **Method:** This article traces the uses of the LCJR from creation to the present and cites lessons learned from its use. **Results:** During the intervening years, the LCJR has been used effectively as a debriefing guide in simulation and as a research instrument, as well as for formative assessment. The LCJR has been translated or is in process in 19 languages besides English. **Conclusion:** This article provides evidence of the efficacy of the LCJR and discusses important lessons learned. [*J Nurs Educ.* 2024;63(3):149-155.]

Clinical judgment in nursing is defined as a way to understand or come to know about a patient's needs, concerns, or health issues leading to a decision about care for the patient, particularly in a poorly defined or unclear situation (Tanner, 2006; Tanner et al., 2022) whereas clinical reasoning is described as the thinking behind clinical judgment (Tanner, 2006). Although not the only model in use, the Tanner Model of Clinical Judgment is the most frequently used clinical judgment model among prelicensure programs in the United States (Jessee et al., 2023). The LCJR is based on the four stages of clinical judgment the Tanner Model describes: (1) noticing; (2) interpreting; (3) responding; and (4) reflecting. At first glance, it might appear that the LCJR is an assessment tool for clinical judgment, but clinical judgment, according to Tanner, is much more complex than

NCSBN, licensure exam (NCLEX)

- Widely used in and outside the US
- Summative evaluation, high stakes
- Assurance of competency (cognitive) for public protection, coupled with educational experience
- Before 2023, MCQ questions often had no associated context
- NCSBN Clinical Judgment Measurement Model (CJMM) was published (Dickison, et al., 2019), anticipating a “next generation” NCLEX in 2023
- CJMM integrated at least three of the previous models of thinking

Figure 1. The National Council of State Boards of Nursing-Clinical Judgment Model.

Next Gen NCLEX

- Unfolding case studies/vignettes; 6 questions develop and assess a situated judgment process
- “Exhibits” set the context/situation (resembles information in Electronic Healthcare Records software)
- Uniform approach to achieve reliable measurement
- Each examinee receives three case studies; additional situated judgment questions are administered as needed to reach a competency decision

References

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